

ASSESSMENT OF COMPLIANCE WITH DAO 224-21 GUIDELINES ON ENTILATION TO MANAGE THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC: BASIS FOR VENTILATION SYSTEM IMPROVEMENT IN A PHARMACEUTICAL PLANT

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ABSTRACT

Many people way of life have been affected by the COVID-19 coronavirus disease. Restrictions, lockdown, health and safety precautions, and restrictions by national and local government agencies were implemented to control the spread of the COVID-19 virus. Economies of several nations are also affected by this COVID-19 pandemic due to the restrictions, lockdown, health and safety precautions. The study utilized the guidelines and questionnaire of the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE DAO 224-21) Guidelines on the Ventilation on Workplaces to Prevent the Spread and Control of the COVID-19 to collect primary data. To determine the relevant provisions on the DOLE DAO 224-21, experts from the DOLE Guidelines and HVAC Engineer were engaged. The 25 employees from Engineering Department were the respondents to evaluate the level of compliance of the pharmaceutical manufacturing plant. The study provides valuable insights into the current state of Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE DAO 224-21) Guidelines on the Ventilation on Workplaces to Prevent the Spread and Control of the COVID-19 implementation in a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant and highlight the importance of the compliance in the pharmaceutical manufacturing industry to prevent the spread of COVID-19

Keywords: *DOLE DAO 224-21, HVAC Compliance, COVID-19 Ventilation Compliance, Quantitative, Pharmaceutical Plant*

INTRODUCTION

Nature and Scope of the Problem Investigated

The COVID-19 pandemic, which is caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus, has posed serious challenges for a variety of international organizations and local businesses. Since the virus is mostly transmitted by respiratory droplets and aerosols, effective ventilation in indoor workplaces has been emphasized as an essential method to reduce the virus' spread. (Chen, X,et.al 2020) In response to the COVID-19 pandemic, the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) published DAO 224-21 regulations on ventilation in workplaces. These standards include recommendations and requirements for ventilation systems in various establishment types, including pharmaceutical manufacturing plants. Since the pharmaceutical industry is crucial in ensuring the continuous production and supply of important medications, keeping a secure workplace for its employees is necessary during the pandemic

Research Objectives

This study addressed the following:

- The relevant provisions of the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on heat, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in times of pandemic. a.) Non-Air-Conditioned Space b.) Air-Conditioned Space c.) Local Exhaust Ventilation (LEV) d.) Restroom and Water Closets e.) Ventilation Assessment f.) Monitoring g.) Operations & Maintenance.
- Level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines order on HVAC during pandemic (Based on the self-assessment made by the participants) a.) Non-Air-Conditioned Space b.) Air-Conditioned Space c.) Local Exhaust Ventilation (LEV) d.) Restroom and Water Closets e.) Ventilation Assessment f.) Monitoring g.) Operations & Maintenance
- Measures that could be recommended to improve the level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE's order on HVAC during pandemic

Research Framework

The Theory of Regulatory Compliance focus on the degree to which a company, person, or other entity complies with the laws, rules, policies, and regulations outlined in a particular program. (Fiene, R. 2016) It was used and applied to this research work. A research framework was developed based on the research questions focusing on the compliance to the DOLE DAO 224-21

Figure 1: Research Framework

Research Significance

The significance of the study aims to evaluate the regulatory compliance to ensure the safe and healthy workplace in a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant during the COVID-19 pandemic. The study aims to find opportunities for improvement in the heat, ventilation and air conditioning (HVAC) systems by evaluating the level of compliance of this pharmaceutical manufacturing plant in relation to the DOLE DAO 224-21 recommendations. The control of the spreading of COVID-19 transmission in a pharmaceutical manufacturing set-up was mitigated by following the guidelines of DOLE DAO 224-21. The study's results and recommendations could help pharmaceutical manufacturing companies in improving their ventilation systems, implementing adequate controls, and implementing into action effective heat, ventilation and air conditioning practices to mitigate the risk of COVID-19 transmission among employees.

Philosophical Lense

Pragmatism is the philosophical underpinning for evaluating how much a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant's optimized heat, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) corresponds with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on workplace ventilation to prevent the spread and control of COVID-19. Practicality and action-oriented approaches to problem-solving are prioritized by pragmatic thinking. In this evaluation, a pragmatic

philosophical approach acknowledges the significance of setting together efficient HVAC systems to stop COVID-19 transmission in the workplace. It focuses on how the rules are really put into practice. A philosophical foundation known as pragmatism places a strong emphasis on action, practicality, and the effects of that activity. In addition to putting a strong emphasis on problem-solving and obtaining desired results, it emphasizes the practical application of information.

Scope and Limitation

The scope and limitations of the study cover the assessment of compliance with the specific DAO 224-21 guidelines. The study's main objective is to describe how closely a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant follows these guidelines for heat, ventilation, and air conditioning to prevent the spread of COVID-19 in their workplaces.

Definition of Terms

The following terms were defined operationally and conceptually to provide readers with a clear understanding of the study:

Air change per hour (ACH) – It defines how frequently the whole volume of air in an area is changed with fresh air in a period of one hour.

Carbon dioxide (CO₂) – Monitoring carbon dioxide levels in workplace areas provides information about occupant presence and ventilation efficiency.

Contaminants – Any compounds or particles in the air that can adversely affect indoor air quality and possibly offer a health risk to occupants like COVID-19 viruses

Cubic feet per minute (CFM) – It corresponds to a specific volume of air flowing through a passage per minute.

Enclosed spaces – It may or may not have windows that could be freely opened.

General ventilation – It can be provided through natural and/or mechanical methods. Dilution ventilation, through natural, mechanical ventilation or both, should be considered as primary engineering control.

Review of Pertinent Literatures

Significant changes in the workplace have resulted from the COVID-19 pandemic, including the requirement for businesses to take precautions in place to prevent the virus from spreading. An essential industry that is essential to the fight against the pandemic is the pharmaceutical industry. However, considering the nature of their operations, pharmaceutical manufacturing companies encounter specific challenges in preventing the spread of COVID-19 in their work environments. (Zhong, L. et.al 2020) The airborne spread of SARS-CoV-2 in indoor conditions is significantly influenced by relative humidity (%RH). (Ahlawat et al. 2020) Ventilation can be used to stop the transmission of airborne infections. (Escombe et al. 2007) To prevent the spreading of COVID-19 disease and to mitigate it, the Department of Labor and Employment (DOLE) has published guidelines on ventilation in places of work. These recommendations have the objective of making

sure that companies take appropriate measures to stop the virus from spreading within their workplaces. To stop the spread of COVID-19 in the workplace and ensure the health and safety of employees, compliance with these guidelines is important (DOLE 2021). This study aims to assess if a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant is following the DOLE guidelines for workplace ventilation to prevent the transmission of COVID-19 viruses. The ventilation system, workplace air quality, and compliance monitoring will all be the main topics of the study. The findings of this study can be useful for determining the degree to which a pharmaceutical manufacturing company complies to the DOLE ventilation recommendations. The results of the study could additionally point out areas for improvement and offer recommendations for enhancing compliance to the guidelines, eventually reducing the risk of COVID-19 transmission in the workplace. The results of the research may help build more practical guidelines for preventing the spread of COVID-19 in the workplace, particularly in pharmaceutical companies.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The research process was focus on identifying the relevant provisions of the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on heat, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant time of pandemic, determine the level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines order on HVAC during pandemic and to recommend supplemental suggestions for gaps to improve. It was aimed to focus at identifying the compliance of the pharmaceutical manufacturing plant to the Department of Labor and Employment DAO 224-21 Guidelines on Ventilation on Workplaces to Prevent the Spread and Control of the COVID-19 by measuring the availability of important practices and resources in survey interviews from the engineering department employees. From the results of these data, we were able to measure the compliance of the pharmaceutical manufacturing plant to the Department of Labor and Employment DAO 224-21 Guidelines on Ventilation on Workplaces to Prevent the Spread and Control of the COVID-19.

Research Locale

The research study was conducted in a pharmaceutical company in Biñan Laguna. This pharmaceutical plant is a state-of-the-art facility, designed to produce a variety of products including prescription medicines in major therapeutic categories in tablet, capsule, powder, ointments, and non-steroidal creams format and liquids products in syrup, suspension, and drops format.

Population and Sampling Design

In determining the relevant provisions of the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on heat, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in times of pandemic in a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant, experts from Department of Labor and Employment and

Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Engineering Department representatives were invited to determine these relevant provisions. The whole population was considered in the collection, measurement, and analysis of data of the engineering department employees' perceptions and the assessment of compliance of the pharmaceutical manufacturing plant to the Department of Labor and Employment DAO 224-21 Guidelines on Ventilation on Workplaces to Prevent the Spread and Control of the COVID-19. The population consisted of all the 25 (twenty-five) engineering department employees. They all participated in the survey interview. In this study, the total enumeration approach was used in the respondents and data samples. Total enumeration provides a complete and accurate picture of the HVAC systems perceptions of the respondents.

Research Instrument

An expert from the Department of Labor and Employment and a representative from the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Engineering Department were asked to determine the relevant sections of the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on heat, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in times of pandemic in a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant. A survey questionnaire was devised by the researcher from the Department of Labor and Employment DAO 224-21 Guidelines on Ventilation on Workplaces to Prevent the Spread and Control of COVID-19 and an assessment tool was utilized to gather the necessary data for this study. The researcher used a quantitative research method that uses a questionnaire. This questionnaire was based on how to answer the research questions.

Data Gathering Procedure

Primary data were collected using the survey questionnaire to be answered by all the 25 (twenty-five) engineering department employees from a pharmaceutical manufacturing company. The researcher will observe the natural setting and perception of the population with regards to their experience in the level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines order on HVAC during pandemic. Total enumeration of all 25 (twenty-five) engineering department employees from a pharmaceutical manufacturing company. These engineering department employees have technical knowledge, skills, and competency in Heat, Ventilation and Air Conditioning.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Representative from Department of Labor and Employment and Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant HVAC Engineer had determined the relevant provisions of the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on heat, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in times of pandemic in a Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant. Based on the assessment done, in section D. Restrooms and Water Closets, Sec. D., No. 2 - "When toilets/water closets are used, close the toilet bowl seat lid before flushing, if available. This aims to minimize the release of droplets into air caused by flushing" and Sec. D., No. 3 "Do not use hand blowers or jet dryers as it contributes to the dispersion of potential contaminated air inside the restrooms" are not relevant in the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on heat, ventilation,

and air conditioning (HVAC) in times of pandemic in a Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant. These items are remove in the instrument survey questionnaire. The participants who responded in the survey shows there perception on the level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines order on HVAC during pandemic.

Table No. 1: Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces

A. Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces	Level of Compliance					SUMS OF RANKS	OVERALL COMPLIANCE LEVEL
	1	2	3	4	5		
1. Maximize natural ventilation through the use of doors, windows and other openings, if possible, to do so.	0	0	0	19	6	106	HIGH COMPLIANCE
2. Ensure that the natural air brought into the workplaces is free of contaminants. If natural ventilation is not feasible or inadequate, fans and air-conditioning system to supply fresh and extract contaminated air shall be used as mechanical ventilation.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
3. Dilution ventilation must be done through use of exhaust fans to achieve an air change rate of 6 to 12 ACH, while maximizing natural ventilation through the use of doors, windows and other openings, if possible and safe to do so.	0	0	0	17	8	108	HIGH COMPLIANCE
4. Exhaust fans should be kept continuously open as much as possible.	0	1	5	16	3	96	HIGH COMPLIANCE
5. If the use of ventilating fans is unavoidable, increase outdoor air changes by opening windows and other openings. Air flow direction or movement should be considered in the layout of work stations to avoid person to person viral spread through airborne respiratory droplets.	0	0	0	16	9	109	HIGH COMPLIANCE
6. Conduct weekly cleaning of windows, other openings, and ventilating fans or as necessary	0	0	5	17	3	98	HIGH COMPLIANCE

Table No. 2: Air-Conditioned Spaces

B. Air-Conditioned Spaces	Level of Compliance					SUMS OF RANKS	OVERALL COMPLIANCE LEVEL
	1	2	3	4	5		
1. For HVAC systems, outdoor air supply should conform to the recommended breathing zone ventilation rates, for the purpose of general air dilution and comfort control.	0	0	0	19	6	106	HIGH COMPLIANCE
2. Run the ventilation system for at least 30 minutes before and after spaces are occupied.	0	1	3	18	3	98	HIGH COMPLIANCE
3. In workplaces that only have local air conditioning units, dilution ventilation may be done through the use of exhaust fans, and filters MERV 13 or higher, or high-efficiency particulate air (HEPA) filter rating applicable to the unit may be installed. Ensure that enough exhaust fans relative to the room volume are available to have the required breathing zone minimum ventilation rates.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
4. Where ventilation is greatly recirculated or access to outside air is not feasible, filters such as HEPA filtration air purifiers can be used to clean recirculated air, provided that the unit is adequate for the size of the room in which it is installed in. Ensure proper maintenance by following manufacturers recommendations of these devices.	0	0	0	21	4	104	HIGH COMPLIANCE
5. Keep the louvers of local air conditioning units in an upward position to prevent the air flowing from one person to another, while observing minimum health protocols.	0	0	0	21	4	104	HIGH COMPLIANCE

6. Frequently open the windows, doors, and other opening to supplement the mechanical ventilation systems to achieve dilution.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
7. Establish a cleaning and maintenance program for mechanical systems. Ensure that no molds or stagnant water will be circulated in the atmosphere. Filters must be changed when necessary. Appropriate personal protective equipment must be worn by workers involved in the cleaning and maintenance.	0	1	2	20	2	98	HIGH COMPLIANCE

Table No. 3: Local Exhaust Ventilation

C. Local Exhaust Ventilation (LEV)	Level of Compliance					SUMS OF RANKS	OVERALL COMPLIANCE LEVEL
	1	2	3	4	5		
1. The LEV system shall conform to the existing local code. It shall have the basic components of hood, ductworks, air cleaning device, fans or blowers and exhaust stack. All installed LEV shall be equipped with a proper air cleaning device to treat, filter and minimize airborne contaminants being exhausted to the atmosphere.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
2. Continuous operation of LEVs when workers are present in order to allow additional air change in the workplace. Ensure that running hoods of LEVs are properly secured when not being used during a specific operation to avoid disruption.	0	0	4	18	3	99	HIGH COMPLIANCE

Table No. 4: Restrooms and Water Closets

D. Restrooms and Water Closets	Level of Compliance					SUMS OF RANKS	OVERALL COMPLIANCE LEVEL
	1	2	3	4	5		
1. Ensure the exhaust fans in restroom facilities are functional and operational at full capacity whenever the building is occupied.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE

Table No. 5: Ventilation Assessment

E. Ventilation Assessment	Level of Compliance					SUMS OF RANKS	OVERALL COMPLIANCE LEVEL
	1	2	3	4	5		
1. Qualified personnel shall ensure that the ventilation system is working or functioning during the conduct of assessment in order to determine how air enters and exits from the space. Other measures to assess could include, but not limited to lingering smell, stuffiness of room, feeling of high humidity or smokiness of room.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
2. The use of natural or mechanical ventilation or the combination depends on the ventilation assessment conducted by a trained safety officer or ventilation/indoor air quality specialist.	0	0	0	19	6	106	HIGH COMPLIANCE
3. For air movement, the directional airflow and objectionable air drafts shall be considered. Airflow direction should be from cleaner source to prevent contaminant transmission.	0	1	0	20	4	102	HIGH COMPLIANCE

4. Carbon Dioxide (CO2) is commonly used as surrogate indicator for assessing indoor air quality (IAQ) and ventilation efficiency. CO2 concentration shall not exceed 1,000ppm. To achieve this, the minimum ventilation in breathing zones as set by the Philippine Green Building Code, could be used as a guide. CO2 level inside an enclosed space may determine using calibrated CO2 monitoring devices, During CO2 monitoring, position the device strategically in locations such as those far from windows, doors and other openings. A calibrated CO2 monitor shall be used to ensure reliability of results.	0	0	2	17	6	104	HIGH COMPLIANCE
5. Ventilation measurements shall be performed internally by the trained safety officer or EHS personnel of the company, DOLE-OSHC or by DOLE accredited WEM Service Providers	0	0	0	19	6	106	HIGH COMPLIANCE

Table No. 6: Monitoring

F. Monitoring	Level of Compliance					SUMS OF RANKS	OVERALL COMPLIANCE LEVEL
	1	2	3	4	5		
1. As provided for in the DTI-DOLE JMC 20-04, the OSH Committee and/or safety officer of the workplace overseeing the enforcement and monitoring of the minimum public health standards for COVID-19 prevention in the workplace, shall include in its OSH program the monitoring and evaluation on the implementation of this guidelines, at least on a monthly basis or as frequently as possible based on the assessment and recommendation of the OSH committee/safety officer.	0	0	0	16	9	109	HIGH COMPLIANCE

2. The DOLE Regional Offices shall monitor compliance with this guideline. Other government agencies shall likewise conduct its own monitoring based on their regulatory functions, as applicable. In case of violation or non-compliance, the applicable sanctions/penalties under pertinent laws, rules and regulations shall be imposed.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
3. Rendering of Technical Assistance - The DOLE, DOH, DTI & DPWH, DILG, DOTr, DOT and the private sector partners shall extend technical assistance and support to employers and workers, and in all workplaces in complying with this guidelines.	0	0	0	19	6	106	HIGH COMPLIANCE

Table No. 7: Operation and Maintenance

G. Operation & Maintenance	Level of Compliance					SUMS OF RANKS	OVERALL COMPLIANCE LEVEL
	1	2	3	4	5		
1. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: Windows are kept open, are clean - free from all types of dust / debris	0	0	0	19	6	106	HIGH COMPLIANCE
2. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: There are no lingering smell, stuffiness of room, feeling of humidity, and/or smokiness of room	0	1	0	20	4	102	HIGH COMPLIANCE
3. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Non Air- Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: The nearby space of the openable windows are free from toxic gases and other pollutants.	0	0	2	17	6	104	HIGH COMPLIANCE
4. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: There are ventilating fans that are installed where fresh air cannot be obtained by natural ventilation.	0	1	5	16	3	96	HIGH COMPLIANCE

5. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Supply-only ventilation fans are installed where fresh air cannot be obtained by natural ventilation.	0	0	0	16	9	109	HIGH COMPLIANCE
6. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Exhaust fans are continuously running during occupancy.	0	0	5	17	3	98	HIGH COMPLIANCE
7. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Air flow from intake to exhaust provides fresh ventilated air to all occupied workspaces.	0	0	3	19	3	100	HIGH COMPLIANCE
8. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Non-Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Number of exhaust fans is enough with respect to the volume of the room to have air change.	0	1	3	18	3	98	HIGH COMPLIANCE
9. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: HVAC system or air conditioning (AC) unit provides outdoor air and is maintained free from dust, molds, etc.	0	0	2	20	3	101	HIGH COMPLIANCE
10. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Air handling unit (AHU) or AC unit uses and can handle MERV 13 or higher filter rating and regular change/cleaning of filters are done and louvers are in upward position.	0	0	1	21	3	102	HIGH COMPLIANCE
11. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Exhaust fans (wall mounted, kitchen, hoods, etc.) are installed (if applicable in the HVAC design).	0	0	2	21	2	100	HIGH COMPLIANCE
12. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: There are no lingering smells, stuffiness of room, feeling of humidity, smokiness of room.	0	0	0	21	4	104	HIGH COMPLIANCE
13. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Windows, doors or other openings can be	0	1	2	20	2	98	HIGH COMPLIANCE

or are regularly opened to increase ventilation.							
14. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning - For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Ventilating fans, or portable air purifier, if used, has HEPA filters and does not blow air from person to person.	0	1	2	20	2	98	HIGH COMPLIANCE
15. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Airflow from intake to exhaust provides fresh ventilated air to all workplaces without objectionable drafts.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
16. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Air change per minute within occupied workspaces maintains CO2 levels below 1,000 ppm at all times.	0	0	0	20	5	105	HIGH COMPLIANCE
17. Heat Ventilation and Air Conditioning: For Air-Conditioned Spaces / Workplaces: Indoor room temperature has no sudden variations or is not excessively hot or cold.	0	0	2	20	3	101	HIGH COMPLIANCE

Based on the results gathered, the relevant provisions in the DOLE DAO 224-21 have a high level of compliance. Gaps were determined based from the respondents. By implementing the measures regarding monitoring procedures, frequent inspections, back-up units, additional manpower, service units, attendance and assessment schedule, calibration device and additional service providers, overseeing schedule, inspection and monitoring plan, establishing information cascade, spare parts management, and employee deployment plan, the pharmaceutical manufacturing plant can increase compliance with DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines, thereby ensuring a safer and healthier work environment for all employees.

Conclusions

The experts from the field have determine the relevant provisions of the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines on heat, ventilation, and air conditioning (HVAC) in times of pandemic in a pharmaceutical manufacturing plant. These relevant provisions were the basis on how to assess the level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines order on HVAC during pandemic.

It has been found out that the level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines order on HVAC during pandemic is highly

compliant. The result of the survey that was conducted in this pharmaceutical company for the level of compliance of the Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant with the DOLE DAO 224-21 guidelines order on HVAC during pandemic was high.

Based on the data gathered, the results are acceptable. We can say that the data is satisfactory since the engineering employees who participated in the survey are already working in the company for many years already and they are present during the time of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Recommendations

Based on the gathered literature, quantitative findings, and conclusions of this study, the researcher recommended to further explore the study on the compliance of a pharmaceutical company in the DOLE DAO 224-21, the following recommendations are suggested:

- A discussion to the top management is encouraged to achieve fully compliant level of compliance.
- This study focuses on a Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant. It is recommended to expand it and include for the future study, more pharmaceutical plants to get the level compliance of other pharmaceutical manufacturing plants.
- It is recommended to explore other HVAC guidelines to prevent the spread of COVID-19 to compare this study.
- This study involved 25 Engineering Department employees in a Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant. It is recommended to include other stakeholders in the future studies to have a more approach and perspective.
- This study was conducted in a Pharmaceutical Manufacturing Plant. It is also recommended to conduct a study on different industries.
- For future similar studies, it is recommended to use other methods of research, such as qualitative research and mixed methods research.
- It is also recommended for future studies to consider the position and views of the Outliers.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The researcher complied with the basic standards of research ethics and also followed the Data Privacy Act in the collection and process of data gathered.

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